

Complexation equilibria of sulfisoxazole with proton and some metal ions in aqueous-organic solvents

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Abstract : The proton-ligand stability constant ($\log K_1^H$ i.e. pK_a) of sulfisoxazole in 50 : 50 (% v/v) aqueous ethanol and 50 : 50 (% v/v) aqueous-dioxane mixtures at different ionic strengths (0.05, 0.10 and 0.15 mol dm⁻³) and its stability constants with some metal ions were determined in 50 : 50 (% v/v) aqueous ethanol and aqueous-dioxane mixtures at 25 ± 0.1 °C and 0.15 mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄) ionic strength. The pK_a value decreases with increasing ionic strength of the medium. Based on $\log \beta_2$ values the stability of the metal complexes follow the order : Mn^{II} < Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Zn^{II} < Cu^{II} < UO₂^{II} < VO^{II} in each aqueous-organic mixture.

Keywords : Sulfisoxazole, ionization constant, stability constants.

N¹-Substituted compounds of sulfanilamide are well known sulfa drugs. Among these sulfisoxazole [*N*¹-(3,4-dimethylisoxazole-5-yl)sulfanilamide] (SUL) has a broad spectrum of bacteriostatic activity affecting gram +ve, gram -ve and many protozoan organisms¹ and is commonly used for treating urinary tract infections and treatment of kidney disease, peduncle disease, bacterial cold-water disease, columnaris and furunculosis². Sulfisoxazole when administered to treat urinary tract infections, remain intact in human blood³. Consequently, the possibility of interaction of metal ions present in the body fluid with the drug cannot be ruled out. The present communication reports the complexation equilibria of sulfisoxazole with proton in dioxane-water and ethanol-water (50 : 50 % v/v) at three different ionic strengths (0.05, 0.10 and 0.15 M). The stability constants of sulfisoxazole with VO^{II}, UO₂^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Mn^{II} ions have been determined by pH-titration technique⁴ at 25 ± 0.1 °C and 0.15 M (NaClO₄) ionic strength in 50 : 50 (% v/v) aqueous ethanol and 50 : 50 (% v/v) aqueous-dioxane medium.

Results and discussion

Sulfisoxazole has one potentially ionisable functional group (-SO₂NH-) and behaves as a monoprotic acid. The ionization constant (pK_{a1}) corresponds to the ionization of a proton from nitrogen of -SO₂NH- group (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Sulfisoxazole : (1, SUL; 2, SUL⁻).

The proton ligand stability constant ($\log K_1^H$ i.e. pK_a) values for sulfisoxazole in different aqueous-organic media lie in the range of 5.61–7.89 (Table 1). For the same (% v/v) composition (50 : 50 aqueous ethanol and 50 : 50 aqueous-dioxane mixtures), pK_a values follow the sequence : dioxane-H₂O > ethanol-H₂O. This trend can be explained on the basis of lower dielectric constant of dioxane-H₂O as compared to ethanol-H₂O system and proton solvation properties of the media⁵. Also, it should be noted that as predicted by Born equation⁶, the creation of charge in media of low dielectric constants is an unfavourable process, hence resulting in higher pK_a values i.e. less acidic character.

According to above equilibria, ionisation of SUL produces anion. The conjugate acid from the solvent is a cation that is stabilized by association with other solvent molecules, a

Table 1. Proton-ligand stability constant ($\log K_1^H$ or pK_{a1}) of sulfisoxazole in dioxane : water and ethanol : water (50 : 50 % v/v) mixtures at 25 ± 0.1 °C and in three different ionic strengths, 0.05, 0.10 and 0.15 mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄)

Ionic strength (mol dm ⁻³)	Dioxane : water :: 50 : 50 (% v/v) $\log K_1^H$	Ethanol : water :: 50 : 50 (% v/v) $\log K_1^H$
0.05	7.894	6.858
0.10	6.872	6.125
0.15	6.023	5.613
0.00	9.125	7.505

phenomenon called solvation. The conjugate base of the acid is an anion that in most cases is also stabilized by solvation. In the present investigations, SUL behaves as stronger acid in ethanol-H₂O mixture (lower pK_a values) in comparison to dioxane-H₂O mixture. This can be explained on the basis of higher dielectric constant (ϵ) of ethanol-H₂O (50 : 50 % v/v, $\epsilon = 52.15$) as compared to dioxane-H₂O (50 : 50 % v/v, $\epsilon = 41.10$) system, since solvents having large dielectric constants favour charge formation and separation. The enhancing proton solvation properties of ethanol as compared to dioxane also account for lower pK_a values in ethanol. The present results indicate that log K₁^H (pK_a) value decreases with an increase of ionic strength. At higher ionic strength, charge separation is encouraged with a concomitant lowering of protonation constants. Addition of a salt slightly increases degree of ionization of a weak acid i.e. salt effect. This effect occurs because the activities of ions of a weak electrolyte decrease due to interionic attraction for ions of strong electrolytes used for maintaining ionic strength⁷. The equilibrium (SUL \rightleftharpoons SUL⁻ + H⁺) is shifted in the forward direction because the ionic atmosphere stabilizes the ions and this stabilization is greater, the greater the ionic strength.

Table 2. Metal-ligand stability constants of sulfisoxazole in dioxane : H₂O and ethanol : H₂O (50 : 50 % v/v) mixtures at 25 \pm 0.1 °C and 0.15 mol dm⁻³ ionic strength

Cation	Dioxane : H ₂ O :: 50 : 50 (% v/v)			Ethanol : H ₂ O :: 50 : 50 (% v/v)		
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β_2	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β_2
VO ^{II}	4.894	4.142	9.036	4.553	3.523	8.076
UO ₂ ^{II}	4.623	4.041	8.664	4.212	3.404	7.616
Co ^{II}	3.273	2.913	6.186	2.988	2.456	5.444
Ni ^{II}	3.587	2.828	6.415	3.154	2.645	5.799
Cu ^{II}	4.223	3.689	7.912	3.705	2.989	6.694
Zn ^{II}	3.725	3.194	6.919	3.323	2.718	6.041
Mn ^{II}	2.856	2.062	4.918	2.526	1.982	4.508

The \bar{n} values were calculated in the pH range 7.2–7.7, 7.0–7.5, 6.9–7.6, 6.0–6.8, 6.2–6.9, 4.0–5.4 and 3.8–5.2 for Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, UO₂^{II} and VO^{II} respectively and lie in the range 0–2 in each case for both solvent systems. The error limits are ± 0.024 log units for log K₁ and log K₂ values (Table 2). The metal ligand stability constants (log K₁ and log K₂) values were higher in dioxane-H₂O as compared to ethanol-H₂O mixtures. This suggests that coordinate bond formed between metal and ligand has more covalent character in case of 50 : 50 (% v/v) dioxane-H₂O having (lower dielectric constant) as compared to ethanol-H₂O mixtures. The stability constants of the complexes follow the order : Mn^{II} < Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Zn^{II} < Cu^{II} < UO₂^{II} < VO^{II}

which is just the reverse of the order of the cation radii and is in agreement with the Irving-Williams order of stability⁸. Among oxo cations, the higher stability of VO^{II} complexes may be attributed to the participation of 3d orbitals in coordination in contrast to behaviour of 5f orbitals in UO₂^{II}, VO^{II} and UO₂^{II} are hard metal ions while Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Co^{II} and Mn^{II} are borderline metal ions. The potential donor sites on ligand (SUL) are O and N atoms and thus are hard donor sites. The favourable interactions between hard metal ions and hard ligand further account for greater stability of VO^{II} and UO₂^{II} as compared to borderline metal ions.

Experimental

Sulfisoxazole (C₁₁H₁₃N₃O₃S, mol. mass 267.3) was procured from Sigma and its solution was prepared in absolute ethanol as well as in dioxane. Double-distilled water was used in preparation of various solutions. AnalaR grade vanadyl sulphate, uranyl nitrate, cupric nitrate, cobaltous chloride, nickel nitrate, zinc sulphate and manganous chloride were used as such. Solutions of various metal ions were prepared by dissolving their appropriate quantity in water to obtain 0.1 M solution in each case and further dilutions were carried out to get 0.005 M solutions. Aqueous NaOH (0.2 M) was prepared by weighing requisite quantity and standardized against standard 0.2 N oxalic acid. This standardized solution was further used to obtain 0.1 M NaOH in 50 : 50 (% v/v) aqueous ethanol and 50 : 50 (% v/v) aqueous-dioxane mixtures. Sodium perchlorate solutions (0.05, 0.1 and 0.15 M) were prepared by dissolving appropriate quantity in water. Solution of perchloric acid (0.1 M) was prepared in water and standardized against standard 0.1 N NaOH solution. All other reagents used were also of AnalaR grade. A digital pH-meter Model pH 5652A (Electronics Corporation of India Ltd.) with a glass and calomel electrodes assembly, reading up to 0.01 pH units, was used to follow the change in pH during the titrations. A thermostated titration vessel of 50 ml capacity containing 20 ml of solution was used for pH titrations. The electrode system was calibrated using standard buffer solutions of pH 4.00 and 7.00. The empirical corrections to pH meter readings in ethanol and dioxane mediums were accounted⁹. For pH titrations, the following thermostated solutions were titrated against standard 0.1 M NaOH solutions.

Dioxane-H₂O/ethanol : H₂O :: 50 : 50 (% v/v) :

(a) 2 ml 0.1 M HClO₄ + 2 ml 1.5 M NaClO₄ + 10 ml dioxane/ethanol + 6 ml H₂O, (b) 2 ml 0.1 M HClO₄ + 2 ml 1.5 M NaClO₄ + 2 ml 0.01 M SUL + 8 ml dioxane/ethanol + 6 ml H₂O, (c) 2 ml 0.1 M HClO₄ + 2 ml 1.5 M NaClO₄ + 2 ml 0.01 M SUL + 2 ml 0.005 M metal ion solution + 8 ml dioxane/ethanol + 4 ml H₂O.

The plots of pH values against volume of NaOH added were drawn. The values of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL were calculated using the Irving-Rossotti method⁴. From these formation curves, the proton-ligand stability constant ($\log K_1^H$) and metal-ligand stability constants ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) were calculated using the half-integral and linear extrapolation method⁴. Also the Hyperquad 2000 was used to get the refined value of stability constants¹⁰. The value of standard deviation is 0.024.

References

1. A. Burger, "Medicinal Chemistry", Wiley Interscience, New York, 2004.
2. G. Patric, "Medicinal Chemistry", Viva BPL, New Delhi, 2002.
3. K. Florey, "Analytical Profiles of Drug Substances", Academic Press, New York, 1973.
4. H. M. Irving and H. S. Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397; 1954, 2904.
5. M. A. G. Del Vado, G. R. Echevarria, A. Garcia-Espantaleon, J. Donoso, F. Muñoz and F. G. Blanco, *J. Mol. Catalysis*, 1988, **44**, 313; K. Lal, *Talanta*, 1978, **26**, 1171.
6. M. Born, *Z. Phys.*, 1920, **1**, 45.
7. P. Debye, *Physik.*, 1925, **26**, 93.
8. H. Irving and R. J. P. William, *Nature*, 1948, **162**, 746; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.
9. M. Meloun, J. Havel and E. Hogfeldt, "Computation of Solution Equilibria", Wiley, New York, 1988; F. Koseoglu, E. Kihe, E. Canel and N. Yilmaz, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1994, **87**, 293; L. G. Van Uitert and C. G. Hass, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 451.
10. P. Gans, A. Sabatini and A. Vacca, *Talanta*, 1996, **43**, 1739.